

Generative models of whole-brain, surface-based imaging features using artificial neural networks

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Introduction

Data-driven generative modelling aims to learn latent distributions of data that can be subsequently used to generate new data instances in-silico, as samples from these learnt distributions. This can be particularly useful for normative modelling [1,2], where knowing conditional distributions for population data allows inferences for the individual. Feasibility and utility of learning distributions for uni(or low)-dimensional data features has been demonstrated [2]. However, treating multi-dimensional feature spaces (with tens or hundreds of features), that can arguably convey higher discriminatory power and specificity, is more challenging. Deep learning generative approaches, such as variational autoencoders (VAEs) [3] or generative adversarial networks [4] provide unique capabilities for learning complex latent distributions. In this work we demonstrate how tens of surface-based brain connectivity features from a large cohort can be used with a VAE to learn their latent multi-dimensional distribution.

Methods

We built a convolutional β -VAE [3] of connectivity blueprints [5,6] extracted from the young adult Human Connectome Project data ($n=1,022$ subjects) [7]. Connectivity blueprints are $N \times T$ matrices that capture the patterns of how N vertices ($N \sim 4,000$) on the white/grey matter boundary surface mesh connect to T white matter tracts. They therefore comprise of T ($=41$ in our case [6]) surface maps, each corresponding to tract termination points, and we aimed to capture their latent generative distribution across a large subject cohort. Connectivity blueprints are used here as an exemplar, but other combinations of multi-dimensional surface features can be considered.

As the input data are in an irregular sheet in 3D space, we treated each of the T dimensions as a separate channel and projected each of them to a 2D surface using an equirectangular projection [8] (Fig.1A,B). We then used 2D convolutional layers for encoding and decoding, while β controlled in the loss function the balance between reconstruction and KL-divergence from the Normal prior. An ADAM optimiser was used for training (500 epochs allowed convergence, Fig.1C). Random sampling from the trained network could then provide T 2D surface maps that were back-projected to the brain surface mesh.

Results

We first compared the mean and variance of connectivity blueprint multi-channel distribution obtained from real data, against the mean and variance of randomly generated samples from the trained VAEs. Fig.2A shows examples for two tracts/channels. The mean of the distribution was accurately predicted by the VAE, however a small latent space gave a narrow distribution (i.e. samples very close to mean with small variance). This was mitigated by increasing the size of the latent space.

We subsequently explored whether the variance of the learnt distribution reflects aspects of between-subject biological variability. To do so, we encoded subjects into the VAE's latent space (Fig.2A, each subject is a dot on the first two components after dimensionality reduction) and explored whether related groups of subjects cluster together in the latent space. We found that a lower regularisation β in the VAE allows a more interpretable latent space. For instance, when using gender to differentiate connectivity blueprints, the $\beta=0.01$ network allowed clearer separation between male and female brain connectivity patterns (Fig.2B top). We also used family structure in this cohort, as monozygotic twin pairs have more similar connection patterns than dizygotic twins/non-twin siblings and than unrelated subject pairs (Fig.2B bottom left). We indeed found that the distance of the corresponding pairs when projected on the latent space of the $\beta=0.01$ network followed on average this pattern (Fig.2B).

Conclusion

We have shown how an artificial neural network can be used to learn the latent generative distribution of multi-dimensional imaging-derived features, even if these are estimated on irregular cortical surface meshes.

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A) Projecting Surface Data to 2D Maps

B) β -VAE Architecture

$$\text{Loss Function: } \mathcal{L}_{vae} = -\mathbb{E}_{q_\phi(z|x)}[\log p_\theta(x|z)] + \beta * D_{KL}(q_\phi(z|x) || p(z))$$

C) β -VAE Training Curves

FIGURE 1. A) Projection of multi-dimensional brain surface features to 2D maps. White matter tractography was used to compute connectivity blueprints, where T columns represent surface maps of cortical termination points for T tracts (example shows arcuate fasciculus). An equirectangular projection is then used to project the irregularly spaced 3D vertices to a 2D irregular mesh. Nearest neighbour interpolation is then used to project to a regular 2D grid. **B)** The T 2D projected maps are used as inputs to a β -VAE (β controls the weight of the KL-divergence regularisation in the VAE loss function). **C)** Examples of converging training curves for different VAE configurations (latent space: 2048 variables for the first two and 128 for the case on the right).

A) Larger Latent Space → More variance captured

B) Reduced β → Higher Latent Space interpretability

Encoding Connectivity Blueprints of **Males** vs **Females** in Latent Space

Encoding Connectivity Blueprints of **Twins** vs **Unrelated Pairs** in Latent Space

FIGURE 2. A) Comparison of mean and variance of connectivity blueprint distribution from real data (left, $n=1022$ subjects) and VAE-generated samples (middle and right, $n=100$ samples). Examples for two tracts are shown and for two VAEs with different latent spaces. Increasing the dimension of the latent space allows more variance of the data distribution to be captured, as small latent spaces give overconfident predictions. Notice that variance scale for data is 2.5 times higher than for VAE. **B)** Exploring biological interpretability of latent space. *Top:* Connectivity blueprints of all subjects were projected onto the latent space (2048 variables) using the trained VAE encoder. Each subject is a dot projected into the first two PCA components of the latent space. Males and females can be separated using lower VAE regularisation ($\beta=0.01$). *Bottom:* Distance between connectivity blueprints of pairs of twins (monozygotic-MZ & dizygotic-DZ), non-twin siblings (Sib) and unrelated subjects (Unrel), projected in the VAE latent space using tSNE. Unrelated subject pairs appear further than MZ twins (as in data) when using lower VAE regularisation ($\beta=0.01$). Dashed lines correspond to median distance of MZ twins.